

A Human-Centered Dynamic Task Planning Approach for Human-Robot Collaboration

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Abstract—In the new collaborative robotic applications, humans and robots cooperate to accomplish a common job, composed by a set of tasks. In this context, both a proper task scheduling strategy and task execution strategy are important to allow the collaboration. The first addresses the uncertainties of the two agents, while the second ensure safety. However, to make the most of the collaboration, it is also crucial to integrates these strategies. In this paper, we propose an integrated architecture that exploits the task execution information to enrich the task scheduling, improving the overall collaboration.

Index Terms—Human-Robot Collaboration, robot safety, dynamic planning.

I. INTRODUCTION

The new industrial settings are characterized by the presence of shared workspace where human and robot work closely. This new paradigm has led to the updating of safety regulations in order to address these new scenarios [1]. Consequently, many strategies have been developed to deal with safety in HRC [2]–[4]. One of the advantages of HRC is that it allows the execution of tasks that neither the human nor the robot alone can perform. Therefore, the choice of how to allocate the tasks between the two agents plays a fundamental role [5]. A lot of research has been done in this field, modeling the task allocation problem as a nonlinear optimization problem [6]–[8]. However, due to the high complexity, these solution can not handle the dynamic rescheduling. In [9] the authors propose a two-level framework for dynamic rescheduling, handling task failures in a collaborative scenario. However, they consider a constant execution time for both agents, which is a very strong assumption. Other works, instead, analyze the dynamic rescheduling considering only the variability of the human operator [10]–[12]. However, in HRC scenario both the human operator and the robot introduce uncertainties in the schedule. The human behavior, indeed, it is hardly predictable, while the robot has to adapt online its trajectory, avoiding the human and ensuring safety.

In this paper we propose a task planning architecture for HRC scenario that integrates a proper task scheduling strategy and a proper task execution strategy, improving the

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collaboration while ensuring safety during the execution. The main contributions of this paper are:

- A dynamic task scheduling strategy that exploits both the real human behavior and the robot behavior to adapt the schedule.
- A dynamic task execution strategy that explicitly takes into account safety standards, informing about the impossibility to execute a task.
- A novel architecture that mutually integrates these two strategies, improving the overall collaboration.

The architecture and its experimental validation are presented below.

II. TASK PLANNING ARCHITECTURE

We consider a HRC application where two agents, a robot manipulator R and a human operator H , must cooperate in order to perform a job, composed by a set of tasks (T_1, \dots, T_N) . Since there may be precedence constraints between tasks, it is possible to group tasks independent of each other into several layers called levels L_l .

The proposed task planning framework is composed by two different layers:

- 1) **The Scheduling layer**, composed by the **Task Assignment** and the **Dynamic Scheduling**. It is responsible of scheduling the tasks between the two agents, adapting it at runtime.
- 2) **The Execution layer**, composed by the **Trajectory Planning** and the **Trajectory Scaling**. It is responsible of planning collision-free trajectories and scaling online the velocity, ensuring safety.

The overall procedure starts at the scheduling layer, where the task assignment firstly computes the nominal schedule solving the following optimization problem:

$$\begin{aligned} \min_{x, c_l} G &= \sum_{l=1}^L \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{a \in A} w_{ai} x_{ail} + \frac{1}{t_{max}} \sum_{l=1}^L c_l \\ \text{subject to} \\ \sum_{l=1}^L \sum_{a \in A} x_{ail} &= 1 \quad \forall i \in \{1, \dots, N\} \\ \sum_{l=1}^L (w_{Ri} x_{Ril} + w_{Hi} x_{Hil}) &\leq M \quad \forall i \in \{1, \dots, N\} \\ \sum_{i=1}^N t_{ai} x_{ail} &\leq c_l \quad \forall l \in \{1, \dots, L\}, \forall a \in A \\ \sum_{a \in A} \sum_{l=1}^L l \cdot x_{ail} &< \sum_{a \in A} \sum_{l=1}^L l \cdot x_{ajl} \quad \forall i \rightarrow j \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

The term $w_{ai} > 0$ represents the cost required by the agent a , i.e. human or robot, to execute the task T_i . The Boolean variable $x_{ail} \in \{0, 1\}$ determines if T_i is assigned to the respective agent and at what level it must be executed. $t_{ai} > 0$ represents the nominal execution time of T_i on behalf of agent a and t_{max} is the maximum task duration. $c_l > 0$ denotes the cycle time of the l^{th} level. The first constraint guarantees that each task is assigned only once, while the second constraint maximizes the parallelism between the two agents. The last constraint ensures the precedences relationship between the tasks.

At this point, the dynamic scheduler is responsible of adapt at runtime the schedule. To achieve this, it firstly exploits a human tracking strategy to estimate the real execution time and to update the value of the cost function in (1). Subsequently, the dynamic scheduler evaluates online a penalty cost β_i for each task, choosing the most suitable one at the moment. The higher is β_i , the lower the priority. The penalty function is defined as:

$$\beta_i = \Delta G_i + isHA_i + isFA_i + M \cdot prec_i - m \cdot succ_i \quad (2)$$

where ΔG_i represents the variation of the cost function in (1) if the robot performed T_i at this moment. $isHA_i$ and $isFA_i$ are two boolean variables that encode the planning information inside the scheduling procedure. If the human operator is occupying the area of the task it would be better to choose a task that is in another area, setting $isHA_i$ equal to one. Or, if the planner has previously failed, it might be better to perform tasks that are in other areas, so $isFA_i$ is set to one. Lastly, the variables $prec_i$ and $succ_i$ represent the number of precedences and successor tasks that have not yet been concluded. These variables are multiplied by two different constant, M and m , to favor tasks with more successors.

At this point, the assigned task is forwarded to the execution layer, which is responsible of ensure the safety for the human operator. The trajectory planning immediately computes a collision-free trajectory that the robot could ideally execute at maximum speed. It subsequently exploit the human monitoring information to adapt the trajectory if it becomes infeasible [4]. Subsequently, the trajectory is passed to the trajectory scaling, which adapts online the magnitude of the velocity along the path ensuring safety. To this purpose it applies a path-velocity decomposition to the trajectory and it solves online the following optimization problem:

$$\begin{aligned} & \min -\alpha \\ & \text{subject to} \\ & J_{r_i}(q)q'_d(s)\dot{s}\alpha \leq V_{max} \quad \forall i \in \{1, \dots, n\} \\ & \dot{q}_{min} \leq q'_d(s)\dot{s}\alpha \leq \dot{q}_{max} \\ & \ddot{q}_{min} \leq \frac{q'_d(s)\dot{s}\alpha - \dot{q}}{T_r} \leq \ddot{q}_{max} \\ & 0 \leq \alpha \leq 1 \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

$\alpha \in [0, 1]$ is the optimization variable and represents the scaling factor. $J_{r_i}(q) \in \mathbb{R}^{1 \times n}$ is a *modified jacobian* that takes

into account only the scalar velocity of the i -th link towards the human operator. V_{max} is the velocity limit imposed by the safety standards. $\dot{q}_{min} \in \mathbb{R}^n$ and $\dot{q}_{max} \in \mathbb{R}^n$ are the joint velocity lower bounds and the joint velocity upper bounds, respectively. While $\ddot{q}_{min} \in \mathbb{R}^n$ and $\ddot{q}_{max} \in \mathbb{R}^n$ are the acceleration limits. $\dot{q} \in \mathbb{R}^n$ is the actual robot velocity and T_r is the robot execution time.

III. EXPERIMENTS

The proposed two-layered framework has been experimentally validated in a HRC scenario, where a human operator cooperates with a UR10e, a 6-DoF collaborative robot. The human tracking strategy is achieved exploiting five OptiTrack Prime^x cameras¹ and implementing the OE-DTW algorithm. The framework has been also compared with a baseline one that does not exploits any rescheduling strategy. The comparison pointed out that our framework outperform the baseline one, obtaining a schedule which is 10% faster. Moreover, thanks to the mutual communication between the two layers, the proposed framework is capable of handling planning failure. The experiments are presented in more depth in the accompanying video.

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¹<https://www.optitrack.com/>.